

Synthesis of biogenic silver nanoparticles employing *Withania somnifera* and antimicrobial efficacy against selected multidrug-resistant bacteria

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Abstract

Antibiotic-resistant infections often result in long-term or ineffective antimicrobial therapy and worldwide adverse treatment outcomes. Nanotechnological techniques for infectious disease treatments and drug delivery systems have significantly advanced in recent years. The development of biogenic silver nanoparticles using different organisms has been predicted as a novel alternate therapy to infectious disease treatments in recent years. The biological synthesis of silver nanoparticles involves reducing and stabilising metal ions. Plants produce a variety of secondary metabolites with strong reducing potentials and act as a desirable source for the manufacture of silver nanoparticles. In the present study, the biogenic synthesis of silver nanoparticles was fabricated from whole plant powder extract of *Withania somnifera*, a native shrub of the Indian subcontinent. The fabrication of WTNPs was confirmed by the surface plasmon resonance seen at 432 nm. WTNPs were rather spherical-shaped, according to TEM pictures. The biosynthesised Ag NPs had a mean diameter of about 46.3 nm and were naturally crystalline. In this exploration, the spherical WTNPs showed outstanding antibacterial activity. The antibacterial effectiveness of silver nanoparticles was significantly increased by the shape of the WTNPs when combined with plant exudates, and this contributes as an alternate combination treatment to fight against the spread of infections that are caused by multidrug-resistant bacteria.

Keywords: Antibiotic resistance, Multi-drug resistant bacteria, Biogenic silver nanoparticles, Infectious diseases, Antibacterial activity

1. Introduction

The evolution of resistance in pathogenic bacteria to numerous antimicrobial drugs has become a public health concern since fewer effective antimicrobial medicines are available to treat diseases (Huemer *et al.*, 2020; Jasovský *et al.*, 2016). Infections caused by resistant bacteria often lead to ineffective or long-term antimicrobial therapy and adverse treatment results. Recent advancements have witnessed multifold progress in nanotechnology and its nanoparticulate methodologies for disease treatments and drug delivery systems (Hussain *et al.*, 2020). The use of nanoparticles in the administration of drugs owes to their distinctive physical and chemical features that result from unique quantum effects, which are primarily packed up by confined energy levels (Pereira *et al.*, 2020).

There are numerous ways to synthesise nanoparticles from various materials, including physical, chemical, and biological processes, using different liquids and solids as precursors, all of which have advantages and disadvantages (Song & Kim, 2009). However, the necessity to create ecologically benign nanoparticles that do not generate toxic by-products in their fabrication pathway is on the rise. Utilising plant resources has recently emerged as a unique approach for synthesising silver nanoparticles, in addition to the potential of some microorganisms such as bacteria and fungi (Chung *et al.*, 2016; Ovais *et al.*, 2018). This type of synthesis requires many environmentally friendly methods, most of which are biological. Silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) synthesised through biological routes make a vital contribution to environmentally friendly materials in science and technology (Jacob *et al.*, 2017).

Withania somnifera is a small woody shrub and an Ayurvedic herb of the Indian subcontinent. It has been used for thousands of years and is well-known for its many positive health effects. It has also been attributed with names such as Indian ginseng, Indian water cherry and Ashwagandha. *Withania somnifera* has diverse biological implications for different diseases, including arthritis, diabetes, anti-stress, and epilepsy (Mirjalili *et al.*, 2009; Singh *et al.*, 2011). Furthermore, it has been shown that it might reduce the levels of reactive oxygen species, alter mitochondrial functions, control apoptosis, inhibit inflammation, and improve endothelial functions (Mulabagal *et al.*, 2009). Although *Withania somnifera* is used

most frequently in therapeutic and ayurvedic medicinal practices, its bioactive potential underlying in conjugation with nanoparticulate systems against multi-drug resistant mechanisms is limited.

The distinctive characteristics of the nanoparticles that have been developed make them prominent in pharmaceutical and medical applications (K *et al.*, 2011). There has been an increased interest in exploring the antibacterial properties of biogenic nanoparticles synthesised from *Withania somnifera* extracts to create effective antibacterial agents. In this exploration, we are synthesising biogenic silver nanoparticles using *Withania somnifera* extracts and studying the efficacy of these nanoparticles on multi-drug resistant bacterial pathogens.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Preparation of *Withania somnifera* plant extract

The *Withania somnifera* plant was collected from the ayurvedic pharmacy in Srinivasamangapuram, Tirupati, Andhra Pradesh, India. The plant was initially washed twice with tap water and finally with deionised water to remove any dirt and shade dried to detract moisture. Subsequently, the whole plant was chopped, and powder(churnam) was prepared using a blender. 5 g of churnam powder was added to 50 ml of double distilled water. The contents were boiled at 60⁰C for 10 min. The contents were cooled and filtered through the Whatman No.1 filter paper. The filtrate was centrifuged at 1000 rpm for 10 min, and the supernatant was collected. This was regarded as an extract for the synthesis of nanoparticles.

2.2. Synthesis of biogenic *Withania somnifera* silver nanoparticles (WTNPs)

2 ml of the plant extract was added to 50 ml of 1mM Silver nitrate solution. The solution was allowed for the reaction for 10 min. The colourless solution was turned into a light pink colour. The contents were kept for incubation at 37⁰C overnight with constant agitation. The solution was turned into a bright pink colour. This change of colourless to dark pinkish solution indicates the reduction of silver ions in the silver nitrate and confirms the fabrication of WTNPs (Saxena *et al.*, 2012).

2.3. Characterisation of WTNP

2.3.1. UV spectroscopy

The above synthesised biogenic WTNP were studied under UV spectroscopy within a scan range from 300 to 800 nm using Shimadzu UV-Vis Spectrophotometer. After diluting a tiny aliquot of the sample into distilled water, the reduction of pure Ag⁺ ions was determined by observing the UV-Vis spectrum of the reaction medium.

2.3.2. X-ray diffraction analysis

The sample containing WTNP was employed for the XRD investigation using a Shimadzu XRD 7000 X-ray Diffractometer. 20µl of the AgNP were put onto a glass substrate as a thin film of solution and read in an X-ray Diffractometer XRD-6000 Shimadzu analytical, India.

2.3.3. Transmission Electron Analysis

The analysis of the conspicuous shape of WTNP was measured using Hitachi TEM-HF- 3300, 300kV TEM.

2.3.4. Atomic Force Microscopy

The surface, shape and quality characteristics of the synthesised WTNP were analysed from AFM-Nova NT-MDT Solver Next, Russia. The nanoparticle suspension was centrifuged at 10,000 rpm, and the pellet was dissolved in deionised water. A drop of nanoparticle suspension was placed on a clean glass slide and dried in hot air at 60⁰C for 10 min. The thin smear on the glass slide was mounted on the microscope scanner.

2.4. Antibacterial culture preparation

Bacterial pathogenic strains such as *Paenibacillus alvei*, *E. coli MDR*, *Klebsiella MDR*, *Macrococcus equiperficus*, *Shigella boydii*, *Enterobacter hormaechei*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* were collected from the hospital environment Tirupati, AP, India and screened for multi-drug resistant using above antibiotics and their combinations following standard

protocols. All the pathogenic bacterial strains have been recognised by performing standard biochemical tests following clinical and laboratory standards institute guidelines (CLSI, 1999). All detected cultures were transferred to a nutrient agar medium for further research and stored at -20°C . Each bacterial strain was inoculated onto a sterile nutrient agar and allowed to grow for 24 hours at 37°C for pure culture.

A loop of inoculum from a culture cultured for 24 hours was transferred into 5 mL of nutrient broth and exposed for 2 hours at 37°C to create a fresh suspension (2.5×10^{-5} CFU/mL).

2.5. Antimicrobial activity of Biogenic silver nanoparticles (WTNPs)

Bacterial pathogenic strains such as *Paenibacillus alvei*, *E. coli MDR*, *Klebsiella MDR*, *Micrococcus equipercicus*, *Shigella boydii*, *Enterobacter hormaechei*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* were collected from the hospital environment Tirupati, AP, India and screened for multi-drug resistance using above antibiotics and their combinations following standard protocols. All the pathogenic bacterial strains have been recognised by performing standard biochemical tests following clinical and laboratory standards institute guidelines. All detected cultures were transferred to a nutrient agar medium for further research and stored at -20°C . Each bacterial strain was inoculated onto a sterile nutrient agar and allowed to grow for 24 hours at 37°C for pure culture. A loop of inoculum from a culture cultured for 24 hours was transferred into 5 ml of nutrient broth and exposed for 2 hours at 37°C to create a fresh suspension (2.5×10^{-5} CFU/mL).

The agar well diffusion technique was used to test the biogenic AgNPs (WTNPs) for their antibacterial efficacy against the multi-drug resistant clinical bacterial strains mentioned above. The bacterial strains were grown on Mueller Hinton Broth (MHB) at 37°C for 24 h. The colony forming unit (CFU) was made to 2.5×10^{-5} CFU by adjusting it with 0.5 McFarland constant and observing the OD at 600 nm in a UV-vis Spectrophotometer. Then, using a cork borer, wells were created in the Mueller Hinton Agar (MHA) plate where the strains had already been swabbed. Antibiotic, silver nitrate and different concentrations (50 μl and 100 μl) of the synthesised AgNPs (WTNPs) with a concentration of 25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ were added to the respective wells. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 h to observe activity in the form of conspicuous inhibition zones. Three times, the experiments were conducted, and the mean values of zone diameter were recorded.

3. Results

The findings in this study demonstrated that the methodology of synthesis of biogenic silver nanoparticles enabled the reliable and affordable synthesis of WTNPs alongside either energy inputs or very hazardous chemicals. The *Withania somnifera* extract, which served as a capping and stabilising agent, was used to synthesise WTNPs.

UV-Vis spectroscopic analysis was performed to establish the existence of biogenic WTNPs. Excitation of surface plasmon vibrations manifested the dark reddish-pink colour. The analysis was carried out by scanning the samples between 300 and 800 nm, and the maximum value was obtained at 432 nm (Fig-1).

WTNPs' X-ray diffraction study showed (Fig-2) a strong Bragg Diffraction peak at 34.01 corresponding to the plane (111), highlighting the hkl integer planes showing the face-centred cubic structure (JCPDS, file No. 04-0783) of WTNPs, which is consistent with other biosynthetic processes for AgNPs that are environmentally benign and sustainable.

The TEM analysis depicted in Figure- 3a corroborates the AgNP's nano-scale size. The synthesised Biogenic WTNPs have spherical morphology with sizes between 15 and 55 nm. The crystalline nature of WTNPs is depicted in Figure-3b with concentric circles.

Atomic Force Microscopy analysis (Fig-4) has given the average size of WTNPs is 46.3 nm with three-dimensional structures. AFM assessment revealed the fabricated WTNPs' size difference, which enabled them to be easily recognisable, spherical, and resemble a cluster.

In the present study, the antibacterial effects of biogenic WTNPs were assessed against multi-drug resistant pathogenic bacterial strains, including *Paenibacillus alvei*, *E. coli* MDR, *Klebsiella* MDR, *Micrococcus equiperdus*, *Shigella boydii*, *Enterobacter hormaechei*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The agar well diffusion method was employed to examine the antibacterial activity of the biogenic silver nanoparticles synthesised using *Withania somnifera* (WTNPs) (Fig-5 & Fig-6). 50 µl & an increased load of 100 µl of silver nanoparticles were loaded into respective wells of WTNPs50 and WTNPs 100; a positive control of AgNO₃ (Ag), plant extract (PE), and antibiotic (AB) was also loaded into respective wells. Inhibition zones were observed around the wells after incubation.

It was discovered that biologically synthesised WTNP's antibacterial activity varied between bacterial strains. *Paenibacillus alvei* had a mean zone of inhibition of 4 mm, *E.coli* MDR a mean zone of inhibition of 5mm, *Klebsiella* with a mean zone of inhibition of 5mm, *Micrococcus equipercicus* 5mm, *Shigella boydii* 2mm, *Enterobacter hormaechei* 3mm and *Pseudomonas* with a mean zone of inhibition 3mm.

Discussion

Bacterial pathogens are omnipresent and are considered a causative agent of nosocomial infections worldwide (Mancuso *et al.*, 2021). Surveillance of nosocomial bacterial infections has exposed trends of multi-drug resistance in patients (van Duin & Paterson, 2020). The mechanisms of antibacterial resistance in these multi-drug resistant bacteria are underlie by either releasing toxins or progressing to form biofilms. As the resistance of pathogens increases to multiple antibiotics, the world is at a juncture of either stopping using antibiotics or exploring novel alternate antibiotics to curb multi-drug resistance and inhibit the progress of infection (Parmanik *et al.*, 2022). At this juncture, the recent bio-nanotechnology paves the way for developing alternate antibiotics for antibacterial resistance. Nanoparticles are considered essential building blocks of bio-nanotechnology and crucial components for numerous applications and fundamental research in recent years (Jutz & Böker, 2011).

In this study utilising plant extract grown under controlled conditions, we have explored a novel technique for the fabrication of WTNP's. Contrary to synthesis by physical or chemical means, biological synthesis of nanoparticles employing extracts of fungi, bacteria, or plants is more affordable and environmentally benign (Abdulrahman *et al.*, 2016). The synthesis of well-dispersed and ultrafine metal nanoparticles using extracts of *Withania somnifera* is of tremendous interest due to their unique physicochemical characteristics and potential biomedical uses. The findings of synthesised nanoparticles are consistent with the reports made by Das & Smita (2018).

The characterisation of WTNP's using UV-spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction, Transmission Electron Microscopy, and Atomic Force Microscopy analysis reveals that WTNP's are in the range of nano-scale. The colour change from a colourless solution to a

reddish pink colour contributes to surface plasmon resonance excitation of the fabricated biogenic silver nanoparticles (Fayaz *et al.*, 2010). The UV-Vis absorption spectrum acquired peak at 434 nm of the reaction solution indicated the formation of silver nanoparticles from silver ions. The broad peak of UV-Vis absorption spectra is due to different metabolites in the *Withania somnifera* extract present in the reaction solution (Takshak & Agrawal, 2015). A single surface plasmon resonance band indicates the formation of uniform spherical WTNPs. According to the XRD graph studies (Fig-2), the biosynthesised WTNPs have a crystalline character and a face-centred cubic structure (Ganguli *et al.*, 2023). The organic content of the *Withania somnifera* extract can be attributed to minor peaks at lower 2 theta values. Hence, it can be determined that biosynthesised nanoparticles have an organic coating and are surrounded by biomolecules (Das M, 2018). The transmission electron image (Fig-3a & Fig-3b) displayed the fabricated WTNP, which were monodisperse, spherical, and infrequently joined to create stable colloidal nanoparticles. Further, the Atomic Force microscope scanning demonstrated that the WTNP grain morphology and the nanoparticles are spherical. However, the sample contains numerous functional groups, such as the OH and NH groups, which are crucial for the biosynthesis of the WTNP. This study's characterisation techniques confirm that the fabricated WTNP are in nanorange. *Withania somnifera* extract functions as both a reducing agent and a stabilising agent for Ag NPs (Anandan *et al.*, 2019; Saravanakumar *et al.*, 2015).

Further in this exploration, we have employed WTNP to assess the antimicrobial properties against seven distinct (gram-negative and gram-positive) bacteria. Moreover, the bacterial pathogens in this study have strong multi-drug resistance and are pathogenic in hospital infections. *Paenibacillus alvei* is an opportunistic bacterium that invades elderly patients with weak immune systems. *E. coli* is a typical intestinal bacterium that evades patient defences and develops resistance to multiple antibiotics. *Klebsiella* is a non-motile gram-negative bacterium that enhances resistance against host defence systems. *Micrococcus equiperficus* is an aerobic biofilm-forming mesophilic pathogenic bacterium. *Shigella boydii* is a food and contaminated water-borne bacteria that causes dysentery in humans. Enterobacter is a gram-negative bacterium and an important pathogen in healthcare-associated infections worldwide. *Pseudomonas*, an aerobic gram-negative bacterium, a causative of both community and hospital-acquired infections (Bharadwaj *et al.*, 2022; Driscoll *et al.*, 2007)

The silver nanoparticles demonstrated improved antibacterial effectiveness by preventing the above harmful bacterial pathogenic strains from exhibiting inhibition zones. The antibacterial potential of the extract and WTNPs on various multi-drug resistant bacterial strains showed enhanced efficacy when compared to the extract and positive and negative controls (Fig-5 & Fig-6). It is generally known that silver ions and compounds made of silver have potent antibacterial properties (Monteiro *et al.*, 2009). The possible antibacterial mechanism of WTNPs is expected to cause mortality by triggering damage to cell membranes, enhancing membrane permeability, halting protein synthesis and extending the lag phase. In earlier investigations, silver nanoparticles exhibited an antibacterial effect against some microorganisms (Ajitha *et al.*, 2014; Kim *et al.*, 2007).

Bacterial pathogens develop resistance through mechanisms such as employing tailored enzymes, switching the permeability of the outer membrane, transforming target locations, establishing efflux pumps and manipulating metabolic pathways (Aleksun & Levy, 2007). Numerous bacterial infections exhibit underlying drug resistance mechanisms, contributing to their clinical endurance. All species indicate some level of inherent resistance to antibiotics. When exposed to a particular drug, selected factors develop and facilitate the emergence of acquired resistance, either mutation or horizontal gene transfer (Aminov, 2009; Toprak *et al.*, 2011). Continued antibiotic drug usage over time becomes resistant and declines the drug's ability to treat a disease. It is analogous to dose failure or drug tolerance when the drug is not meant to kill or suppress a microorganism (Magiorakos *et al.*, 2012).

Although the problem of antibiotic resistance has increased rapidly in recent years, drug investigation is still progressing slowly. The contamination and the spread of resistant bacteria advancement threaten the occurrence of prevalent infectious diseases that frequently do not respond to conventional therapies (Karam *et al.*, 2016). However, the WTNPs fabricated in this study, due to their unique properties of penetration, contact, and altering microbe membrane permeability, have contributed significantly to the inhibition of MDR pathogens to a significant extent at very low concentrations.

The possible mechanisms of the antibacterial action of WTNPs mainly depend on the bacterial membrane and nanoparticle interaction. The biogenic silver nanoparticles are immobilised onto the bacterial membrane, enhancing the membrane's permeability. In this study, the silver and the biological extract that reduced the silver exerted a synergic effect,

potentially inhibiting bacterial growth (Li *et al.*, 2010). The interaction between silver and some membrane proteins from bacteria is known to inactivate proteins and enzymes that are attached to the membrane (Pal *et al.*, 2007; Reidy *et al.*, 2013). In a similar study explored by Das & Smita (2018), fabricated biogenic silver nanoparticles displayed antimicrobial activities. In a recent study, the biogenic silver nanoparticles fabricated from *Peganum harmala* prevented bacterial biofilm formation, supporting our findings (Al-Momani *et al.*, 2023). Further studies are needed to explore several dimensions of WTNPs as an antibacterial agent.

Conclusion

Contemporary conventional drug limitations include enhanced resistance, unavoidable adverse effects, loss of efficacy from continuous usage, and high expense. With the inevitable advent of multi-drug resistant (MDR) bacterial strains concurrently resistant to various medicines, the range of antibiotics now in use gradually becomes selectively useless. In this work, the inexpensive reduction approach used to fabricate the biogenic silver nanoparticles, WTNPs, holds considerable promise as an antibacterial agent against multi-drug resistant bacterial pathogenic strains. Based on these findings, the WTNPs may be applied to future antibacterial therapeutic applications.

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Figures

Fig:1 - UV Vis spectroscopy depiction of synthesised biogenic WTNPs

Fig:2- XRD micrograph of WTNPs depicting Bragg's reflections of face-centred cubic structure

Fig:3a- TEM image showing the spherical shape of synthesised WTNPs

Fig:3b- TEM image showing SAED pattern of the spherical shape WTNPs

Fig:4- AFM image displaying the topographical data of WTNPs synthesised using *Withania somnifera* extract

Fig:5 - Antibacterial activity of WTNPs against multi-drug resistant bacterial pathogens

Fig:6- Antibacterial activity of WTNPs against MDR bacterial strains

References

- Abdulrahman HB *et al.*, 2016. Biosynthesis of silver nanoparticles and its applications. *Colloids and Surfaces B: Biointerfaces* 6: 1–13. DOI: 10.1155/2015/829526
- Ajitha B, Ashok Kumar Reddy Y, Reddy PS. 2014. Biogenic nano-scale silver particles by *Tephrosia purpurea* leaf extract and their inborn antimicrobial activity. *Spectrochimica Acta - Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy* 121: 164–172. DOI: 10.1016/j.saa.2013.10.077
- Alekshun MN, Levy SB. 2007. Molecular mechanisms of antibacterial multi-drug resistance. *Cell* 128: 1037–1050. DOI: 10.1016/J.CELL.2007.03.004
- Al-Momani H *et al.*, 2023. The efficacy of biosynthesised silver nanoparticles against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* isolates from cystic fibrosis patients. *Scientific Reports* 13 DOI: 10.1038/S41598-023-35919-6
- Aminov RI. 2009. The role of antibiotics and antibiotic resistance in nature. *Environmental Microbiology* 11: 2970–2988. DOI: 10.1111/j.1462-2920.2009.01972.x
- Anandan M, Poorani G, Boomi P, Varunkumar K, Anand K, Chuturgoon AA, Saravanan M, Gurumallesh Prabu H. 2019. Green synthesis of anisotropic silver nanoparticles from the aqueous leaf extract of *Dodonaea viscosa* with their antibacterial and anticancer activities. *Process Biochemistry* 80: 80–88. DOI: 10.1016/J.PROCBIO.2019.02.014
- Bharadwaj A, Rastogi A, Pandey S, Gupta S, Sohal JS. 2022. Multidrug-Resistant Bacteria: Their Mechanism of Action and Prophylaxis. *BioMed Research International* 2022 DOI: 10.1155/2022/5419874
- Chung IM, Park I, Seung-Hyun K, Thiruvengadam M, Rajakumar G. 2016. Plant-Mediated Synthesis of Silver Nanoparticles: Their Characteristic Properties and Therapeutic Applications. *Nano-scale Research Letters* 11: 1–14. DOI: 10.1186/s11671-016-1257-4
- CLSI, 1999. M26-A Methods for Determining Bactericidal Activity of Antimicrobial Agents; Approved Guideline This document provides procedures for determining the lethal activity of antimicrobial agents
- Das M, Smita SS. 2018. Biosynthesis of silver nanoparticles using bark extracts of *Butea monosperma* (Lam.) Taub. and study of their antimicrobial activity. *Applied Nanoscience* 5: 1059–1067. DOI: 10.1007/S13204-018-0721-0
- Driscoll JA, Brody SL, Kollef MH. 2007. The epidemiology, pathogenesis and treatment of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* infections. *Drugs* 67: 351–368. DOI: 10.2165/00003495-200767030-00003
- van Duin D, Paterson DL. 2020. Multidrug-Resistant Bacteria in the Community: An Update. *Infectious Disease Clinics of North America* 34: 709–722. DOI: 10.1016/J.IDC.2020.08.002

- Fayaz M, Tiwary CS, Kalaichelvan PT, Venkatesan R. 2010. Blue orange light emission from biogenic synthesised silver nanoparticles using *Trichoderma viride*. *Colloids and surfaces. B, Biointerfaces* 75: 175–178. DOI: 10.1016/J.COLSURFB.2009.08.028
- Ganguli S *et al.*, 2023. Size controlled biosynthesis of silver nanoparticles using *Ophiorrhiza mungos*, *Ophiorrhiza harrisiana* and *Ophiorrhiza rugosa* aqueous leaf extract and their antimicrobial activity. *Heliyon* 9 DOI: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e16072
- Huemer M, Mairpady Shambat S, Brugger SD, Zinkernagel AS. 2020. Antibiotic resistance and persistence-Implications for human health and treatment perspectives. *EMBO reports* 21 DOI: 10.15252/EMBR.202051034
- Hussain Z, Abourehab MAS, Khan S, Thu HE. 2020. Silver nanoparticles: a promising nanoplatform for targeted delivery of therapeutics and optimised therapeutic efficacy. In *Metal Nanoparticles for Drug Delivery and Diagnostic Applications*. Elsevier; 141–173. DOI: 10.1016/b978-0-12-816960-5.00009-4
- Jacob SJP, Prasad VLS, Sivasankar S, Muralidharan P. 2017. Biosynthesis of silver nanoparticles using dried fruit extract of *Ficus carica* - Screening for its anticancer activity and toxicity in animal models. *Food and Chemical Toxicology* 109: 951–956. DOI: 10.1016/j.fct.2017.03.066
- Jasovský D, Littmann J, Zorzet A, Cars O. 2016. Antimicrobial resistance—a threat to the world’s sustainable development. *Upsala Journal of Medical Sciences* 121: 159–164. DOI: 10.1080/03009734.2016.1195900
- Jutz G, Böker A. 2011. Bionanoparticles as functional macromolecular building blocks e A new class of nanomaterials. *Polymer* 52: 211–232. DOI: 10.1016/j.polymer.2010.11.047
- K S, S G, T R, T B. 2011. Biomedical potential of silver nanoparticles synthesised from calli cells of *Citrullus colocynthis* (L.) Schrad. *Journal of Nanobiotechnology* 9: 43. DOI: 10.1186/1477-3155-9-43
- Karam G, Chastre J, Wilcox MH, Vincent JL. 2016. Antibiotic strategies in the era of multi-drug resistance. *Critical Care* 20: 1–9. DOI: 10.1186/S13054-016-1320-7/TABLES/2
- Kim JS *et al.*, 2007. Antimicrobial effects of silver nanoparticles. *Nanomedicine : nanotechnology, biology, and medicine* 3: 95–101. DOI: 10.1016/J.NANO.2006.12.001
- Li WR, Xie XB, Shi QS, Zeng HY, Ou-Yang YS, Chen Y Ben. 2010. Antibacterial activity and mechanism of silver nanoparticles on *Escherichia coli*. *Applied microbiology and biotechnology* 85: 1115–1122. DOI: 10.1007/S00253-009-2159-5
- Magiorakos AP *et al.*, 2012. Multidrug-resistant, extensively drug-resistant and pandrug-resistant bacteria: an international expert proposal for interim standard definitions for acquired resistance. *Clinical Microbiology and Infection* 18: 268–281. DOI: 10.1111/J.1469-0691.2011.03570.X
- Mancuso G, Midiri A, Gerace E, Biondo C. 2021. Bacterial antibiotic resistance: the most critical pathogens. *Pathogens* 10: 1310. DOI: 10.3390/PATHOGENS10101310/S1

- Mirjalili MH, Moyano E, Bonfill M, Cusido RM, Palazón J. 2009. Steroidal lactones from *Withania somnifera*, an ancient plant for novel medicine. *Molecules (Basel, Switzerland)* 14: 2373–2393. DOI: 10.3390/MOLECULES14072373
- Monteiro DR, Gorup LF, Takamiya AS, Ruvollo-Filho AC, Camargo ER de, Barbosa DB. 2009. The growing importance of materials that prevent microbial adhesion: antimicrobial effect of medical devices containing silver. *International journal of antimicrobial agents* 34: 103–110. DOI: 10.1016/J.IJANTIMICAG.2009.01.017
- Mulabagal V, Subbaraju G V, Rao C V, Sivaramakrishna C, DeWitt DL, Holmes D, Sung B, Aggarwal BB, Tsay HS, Nair MG. 2009. Withanolide sulfoxide from *Aswagandha* roots inhibits nuclear transcription factor-kappa-B, cyclooxygenase and tumor cell proliferation. *Phytotherapy research : PTR* 23: 987–992. DOI: 10.1002/PTR.2736
- Ovais M, Khalil AT, Islam NU, Ahmad I, Ayaz M, Saravanan M, Shinwari ZK, Mukherjee S. 2018. Role of plant phytochemicals and microbial enzymes in biosynthesis of metallic nanoparticles. *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology* 102: 6799–6814. DOI: 10.1007/s00253-018-9146-7
- Pal S, Tak YK, Song JM. 2007. Does the antibacterial activity of silver nanoparticles depend on the shape of the nanoparticle? A study of the gram-negative bacterium *Escherichia coli*. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology* 73: 1712–1720. DOI: 10.1128/AEM.02218-06/ASSET/6C9C03C4-A4A8-46FD-9451-902F4F8671C3/ASSETS/GRAPHIC/ZAM0060775900008.JPEG
- Parmanik A, Das S, Kar B, Bose A, Dwivedi GR, Pandey MM. 2022. Current Treatment Strategies Against Multidrug-Resistant Bacteria: A Review. *Current microbiology* 79 DOI: 10.1007/S00284-022-03061-7
- Pereira TM, Polez VLP, Sousa MH, Silva LP. 2020. Modulating physical, chemical, and biological properties of silver nanoparticles obtained by green synthesis using different parts of the tree *Handroanthus heptaphyllus* (Vell.) Mattos. *Colloids and Interface Science Communications* 34: 100224. DOI: 10.1016/j.colcom.2019.100224
- Reidy B, Haase A, Luch A, Dawson KA, Lynch I. 2013. Mechanisms of Silver Nanoparticle Release, Transformation and Toxicity: A Critical Review of Current Knowledge and Recommendations for Future Studies and Applications. *Materials* 6: 2295. DOI: 10.3390/MA6062295
- Saravanakumar A, Ganesh M, Jayaprakash J, Jang HT. 2015. Biosynthesis of silver nanoparticles using *Cassia tora* leaf extract and its antioxidant and antibacterial activities. *Journal of Industrial and Engineering Chemistry* 28: 277–281. DOI: 10.1016/J.JIEC.2015.03.003
- Saxena A, Tripathi RM, Zafar F, Singh P. 2012. Green synthesis of silver nanoparticles using aqueous solution of *Ficus benghalensis* leaf extract and characterisation of their antibacterial activity. *Materials Letters* 67: 91–94. DOI: 10.1016/j.matlet.2011.09.038
- Singh N, Bhalla M, de Jager P, Gilca M. 2011. An Overview on *Ashwagandha*: A Rasayana (Rejuvenator) of Ayurveda. *African Journal of Traditional, Complementary, and Alternative Medicines* 8: 208. DOI: 10.4314/AJTAM.V8I5S.9

- Song JY, Kim BS. 2009. Rapid biological synthesis of silver nanoparticles using plant leaf extracts. *Bioprocess and biosystems engineering* 32: 79–84. DOI: 10.1007/S00449-008-0224-6
- Takshak S, Agrawal SB. 2015. Alterations in metabolite profile and free radical scavenging activities of *Withania somnifera* leaf and root extracts under supplemental ultraviolet-B radiation. *Acta Physiologiae Plantarum* 37: 1–12. DOI: 10.1007/S11738-015-2014-5/METRICS
- Toprak E, Veres A, Michel JB, Chait R, Hartl DL, Kishony R. 2011. Evolutionary paths to antibiotic resistance under dynamically sustained drug selection. *Nature Genetics* 2011 44:1 44: 101–105. DOI: 10.1038/ng.1034